

**A QUALITATIVE STUDY ON THE TRANSITION TO NORMALCY: CHALLENGES
AND COPING MECHANISMS OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN
RIZAL DIVISION'S PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS
DURING FULL IN-PERSON CLASS IMPLEMENTATION
A CORRESPONDENCE ARTICLE**

Mary Jane C. Rosero

School of Graduate Studies, The National Teachers College
Manila, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408360>

ABSTRACT

This qualitative study explores into the challenges and coping mechanisms employed by junior high school teachers in Rizal Division's public secondary schools during the transition to full-scale in-person classes. Data was meticulously gathered through an exhaustive review of literature, with permissions obtained from authors as necessary. The study's objective is to comprehend the hurdles faced by educators and the adaptive strategies they utilized in response. Findings indicate that teachers tend to employ active coping strategies when confronted with severe challenges. Several themes surfaced regarding their experiences and the trials of in-person classes. This study contributes to the dialogue on educational resilience and adaptive strategies, providing valuable insights for educators, policy makers, and the broader educational community. It stands as a testament to the resilience of the educational community and serves as a guide for future policy-making and the development of support systems

Keywords: *Qualitative Study; Transition to Normalcy; Junior High School Teachers; In-Person Class Implementation; Coping Mechanisms*

INTRODUCTION

In light of the global pandemic, educational institutions across the globe have grappled with unprecedented challenges. As highlighted by Zamani et al. (2022), the Covid-19 pandemic has instigated a significant shift towards online communication technologies in the educational sector. This sudden transition, however, has posed considerable hurdles for the international education community.

As posited by Chatzipanagiotou et al. (2023), the unpredictable nature of the pandemic demanded sensitive and directed leadership from school authorities. Now, as we navigate our way back to normalcy, the complete reinstatement of face-to-face classes in public secondary schools, especially in the Rizal Division, brings forth its own unique set of challenges and requirements. Anero and Tamayo,(2023).

This article presents a qualitative study that explores into these challenges and the coping strategies adopted by junior high school teachers during this crucial phase. The study aimed to comprehend the difficulties encountered by junior high school teachers in the Division of Rizal during the full-scale implementation of in-person classes, and to identify the adaptive measures they employed in this new educational setting.

Incorporating the findings from Honra's (2022) research, the study revealed that when teachers experience a high intensity of challenges in their teaching practices during the pandemic, they tend to adopt active coping strategies indicative of grit and a more practical approach to solving the problem.

The significance of this study lies in its potential contribution to the ongoing discourse on educational resilience and the importance of adaptive strategies in the face of transformative change. The insights gleaned from this research are anticipated to benefit junior high school educators, policy makers, and the educational community at large, thereby fostering a collective understanding of the dynamic nature of teaching in evolving educational landscapes.

Research Questions

The full implementation of in-person classes in the Division of Rizal has presented junior high school teachers with specific challenges. This study aims to identify these challenges and understand the coping mechanisms employed by teachers to adapt to this new educational landscape.

Research question 1: What are the specific challenges faced by junior high school teachers in the Division of Rizal during the full implementation of in-person classes?

Research question 2: What coping mechanisms have teachers employed to adapt to the full implementation of in-person classes?

METHODOLOGY

This correspondence article explores the experiences of junior high school educators in the Rizal Division during the transition from remote to in-person teaching using a qualitative research design. The design was chosen for its ability to provide a detailed and nuanced understanding of the educators' experiences. Instead of collecting primary data through interviews, data was gathered through a comprehensive literature review. The researcher conducted a thorough search for articles, reports, and other relevant literature on the topic, obtaining permission from the authors as necessary. The process involved familiarizing oneself with the data, searching for themes, reviewing these themes, defining and naming them, and finally producing a report.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of schools transitioning back to normalcy, after disruptions of Covid 19 , it's not necessarily an easy process. The goal of this correspondence is to present challenges and demands as well as the coping mechanisms employed by junior high school teachers during this critical period

For research question 1, Anero and Tamayo explored the specific challenges faced by junior high school teachers in the Division of Rizal during the full implementation of in-person classes. Their findings, which are both comprehensive and insightful, shed light on the multifaceted difficulties encountered in the educational field during this transition period (Anero & Tamayo, 2023).

The researchers identified several specific challenges. These included issues related to classroom infrastructure and facilities, learning gaps and academic challenges, behavioral issues and student discipline, safety and security, teacher workload and teaching loads, student engagement and parent involvement, gender-responsive policy and early pregnancy, professional development, and the provision of learning materials (Anero & Tamayo, 2023).

Each of these challenges encompasses a wide range of issues, from infrastructural and logistical concerns to pedagogical and socio-emotional aspects of teaching. This section will discuss these challenges in detail, providing a nuanced understanding of each issue and its implications for educators and policymakers alike.

Classroom Infrastructure and Facilities: The study highlighted the difficulties related to the physical environment of the classrooms and the availability of necessary facilities. This includes inadequate classroom space, lack of proper ventilation, and insufficient sanitation facilities, which have been exacerbated by the pandemic and the need for social distancing measures.

Learning Gaps and Academic Challenges: The transition to in-person classes has revealed significant learning gaps among students, likely due to the disruptions caused by the shift to online learning during the pandemic. Teachers are struggling to meet academic standards and ensure that all students are able to catch up.

Behavioral Issues and Student Discipline: With the return to in-person classes, teachers are facing challenges in managing student behavior and maintaining discipline

in the classroom. This includes dealing with disruptive behavior, absenteeism, and lack of motivation among students.

Safety and Security: Ensuring the safety and security of students during in-person classes is a major concern. This includes implementing health protocols to prevent the spread of COVID-19, as well as addressing issues related to bullying and violence in schools.

Teacher Workload and Teaching Loads: The increased workload and teaching loads for teachers have been a significant challenge. This includes the additional responsibilities related to health protocols, as well as the need to provide remedial lessons for students who have fallen behind.

Student Engagement and Parent Involvement: Engaging students in learning and involving parents in the education process have been difficult. This includes motivating students to participate in class and encouraging parents to support their children's learning at home.

Gender-Responsive Policy and Early Pregnancy: Issues related to gender-responsive policies and early pregnancy among students have also been highlighted. This includes the need for comprehensive sexuality education and support for pregnant students to continue their education.

Professional Development: The need for continuous professional development to adapt to the changing educational landscape is a key challenge. This includes training on new teaching methodologies and technologies, as well as support for teachers' mental health and well-being.

Learning Materials: Providing adequate and appropriate learning materials for in-person classes is a significant challenge. This includes the need for textbooks, workbooks, and other resources that are suitable for in-person instruction.

In conclusion, the study by Anero and Tamayo (2023) provides valuable insights into the complexities of implementing in-person classes in the context of the Division of Rizal. These findings underscore the need for comprehensive strategies and interventions to address these challenges and support teachers in this transition.

For research question 2 Based on the research by Jarom A. Anero and Eloisa S. Tamayo, teachers employed the following coping mechanisms to adapt to the full implementation of in-person classes.

Collaborative Support and Professional Development: Teachers sought support from their colleagues and pursued professional development opportunities.

Resilience and Positivity: Teachers demonstrated resilience and maintained a positive outlook despite the challenges.

Student-Centered Strategies and Interventions: Teachers implemented strategies and interventions that were centered on the needs of the students.

Adaptability and Flexibility: Teachers showed adaptability and flexibility in their teaching methods to cater to the changing educational landscape.

Emphasizing Physical and Mental Health: Teachers emphasized the importance of maintaining physical and mental health amidst the stress and workload.

Effective Communication and Involvement of Stakeholders: Teachers ensured effective communication with all stakeholders and involved them in the educational process.

Innovative Teaching Approaches: Teachers employed innovative teaching approaches to engage students and enhance learning.

Reminding Purpose and Passion: Teachers reminded themselves of their purpose and passion for teaching, which helped them stay motivated.

These coping mechanisms helped them navigate the challenges of transitioning back to in-person classes. The results of the study are largely consistent with the existing literature on teaching and coping mechanisms. The findings provide valuable insights into the experiences of teachers during the full implementation of in-person classes and underscore the importance of support, resilience, adaptability, health, communication, innovation, and motivation in teaching.

Conclusions

The study conducted by Jarom A. Anero and Eloisa S. Tamayo aimed to understand the challenges faced by junior high school teachers during the full implementation of in-person classes and identify the coping mechanisms they employed.

The research revealed that teachers employed various coping mechanisms such as collaborative support and professional development, resilience and positivity, student-centered strategies and interventions, adaptability and flexibility, emphasizing physical and mental health, effective communication and involvement of stakeholders, innovative teaching approaches, and reminding themselves of their purpose and passion for teaching.

These findings suggest that teachers are capable of adapting to changes in the educational landscape and are resilient in the face of challenges. They are willing to learn and grow, and they value the well-being of themselves and their students. They understand the importance of effective communication and stakeholder involvement, and they are not afraid to innovate and try new teaching approaches. Moreover, they are driven by their purpose and passion for teaching.

In conclusion, the full implementation of in-person classes posed challenges to teachers, but they were able to cope through various mechanisms. These findings provide valuable insights for educational institutions, policymakers, and other stakeholders in supporting teachers in this transition. Future research could further explore these coping mechanisms and develop strategies to enhance teacher support systems.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms that the author reviewed this study.

Funding

This work received no specific grant from any funding agency

Acknowledgements

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to Almighty God for strength and guidance. Special thanks to my mother and siblings for their unwavering support, to our colleagues for valuable insights. To my husband, children, daughter-in-law, and grandson, your love and understanding fuelled my perseverance.

REFERENCES

- Anero, J., & Tamayo, E. (2023). Going back to normal: A phenomenological study on the challenges and coping mechanisms of junior high school teachers in the full implementation of in-person classes in the public secondary schools in the Division of Rizal. *Psych Educ*, 12(767-808). Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4550730>
- Chatzipanagiotou P, Katsarou E. Crisis Management, School Leadership in Disruptive Times and the Recovery of Schools in the Post COVID-19 Era: A Systematic Literature Review. *Education Sciences*. 2023; 13(2):118. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13020118> .Retrieved from <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7102/13/2/118#sec6-education-13-00118>
- Honra, Joelash R. (2022). Teachers' Perceived Challenges and Coping Strategies in Pandemic-Influenced Teaching: Basis for a School-Based Teacher Support Mechanism. *International Journal of Education, Learning and Development* 10 (10):57-73. Retrieved from <https://philpapers.org/rec/HONTPC>
- Zamani, A., Mohamad, M., Reesha, A., & Kamarudin, R. (2022). The Impact of Covid-19: A Literature Review on the Challenges in E-Learning. *Creative Education*, 13, 3490-3503. Retrieved from https://www.scirp.org/pdf/ce_2022111815464357.pdf.